

COMPUTATIONAL TREATMENT OF THE HIERARCHY OF GENERAL AND EVOLUTION ALGEBRAS

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Abstract. *The concept of the hierarchy of algebras is not too covered in the literature. Indeed, there are very few works on the hierarchy of algebras in general and almost none for any particular type of algebras. In a previous work by one of the authors, the hierarchy of evolution and Lie algebras was studied and that study was used to extend that concept to the hierarchy of associated graphs, although the computational treatment given to that study was not too extensive. This paper delves into this last aspect, theoretically estimating the worst space and time complexity for general algebras and verifying it empirically. Examples near the worst case have been proposed and executed several times per dimension to get a neat scatter-plot. The polynomial fits which optimize their goodness values follow the predicted theoretical laws. Time complexity has been tested for evolution algebras too, yielding no relevant changes w.r.t. the general case. Finally, a deep study on dependences between complexity and the structure of both the input and the output has been carried out. It has been noticed that intricacy of output structure and execution times are highly correlated. Effect of input structure is much weaker.*

Introduction

There are very few references in the literature on the concept of hierarchy of algebras in general, and even less in the case of particular algebras, such as those of Lie, Leibniz, Morgan, Zimbiel and others equally well known, such as evolution algebras, which, unlike all the previous ones, do not have an identity that characterizes them.

About evolution algebras in particular, it was Tian, who introduced them in his doctoral thesis, who first gave the first notions about their hierarchy in his book in 2008 [2], not having later other references in this respect until Cruz, del Valle, Núñez and Pena returned to this question in [1].

In that article, those authors generalized the concept of hierarchy to any algebra and proved that that concept is an invariant under isomorphism of algebras. In fact, they also introduced a new version of the concept of hierarchy for graphs, which, at present, is still less studied than the one for algebras.

However, in that work the authors do mainly a theoretical study of the question, presenting an algorithm that allowed them obtaining the hierarchy of these algebras, but they only dealt very slightly with the computational aspects of the algorithmic study they carried out, although they did comment that this study remained as an open problem, which they wished to solve in the future.

This paper fills that gap. In it, the authors (one of whom was also the author of that previous article), present a detailed and careful computational study of this issue, addressing computational aspects of the algorithm presented in [1].

The main results of the computational study carried out have been the following. Firstly, it has been proven that the regression for the spatial complexity of the computational treatment of evolution algebras is cubic, as Cruz et al had already conjectured in [1]. To do this, a more powerful computer has been used than the one the authors of that article had used and it has been subjected to random sampling up to dimension 200, in which the measurements are taken separated in time to average the background fluctuations of the base consumption of RAM, ignoring all dispensable programs, all of which produced a definitely very good fit.

Secondly, we have investigated the worst possible case of algebras at a computational level, obtaining several conclusions about the form of these algebras: they must have maximum depth in their hierarchy and produce certain chains in the search set that cause each MPI the corresponding search is maximum. In this regard, an attempt has been made to create a random generator of product rules that meet these conditions, in order to provide more examples of unfavorable algebras. For now, an algebra generator with maximum depth in its hierarchy has been obtained, and the density or sparsity of the elements in the product rules can be modulated to show more and less complicated examples.

Also, regarding the presentation, examples have been represented as follows: the product rules are represented in a tensor of voxels (or cubes) and the hierarchies in matrix color maps. This allows for a simple visual check of the hierarchy and structural complexity

of product rules, although there is little intuition that this can be developed to know whether a more complex structure induces more or less connected hierarchies.

The structure of this paper is as follows: Section 1 is mainly devoted to recall some preliminaries concepts and results on the hierarchy of an algebra in general and of an evolution algebra in particular. Based on the algorithm used by Cruz et al. to carry out the computational treatment of the theoretical study that they did in [1] on the hierarchy of algebras, Section 2 shows the most extensive and deep computational treatment that the authors have carried out on this topic, dealing in 5 different subsections with some aspects of the computational treatment of the algorithm, including in them the worst case time complexity (Subsection 2.1), the average runtime growth of a general algebra (Subsection 2.2), the effect of input and output structure on runtimes (Subsection 2.3), the complexity for evolving algebras (Subsection 2.4) and the space complexity (Subsection 2.5). Some examples of algebras and their hierarchies are given in Section 3 and some conclusions in Section 4 followed by the corresponding bibliography used close this contribution.

1 Preliminaries

So that this paper was self-contained, we recall in this section some basic concepts and properties of evolution algebras. For further information, the reader can consult [2, 3], for instance.

1.1 Evolution algebras

Let E be an algebra (not necessarily associative) over a field K , endowed with the multiplication law and let $e_i, i \in \Lambda$ be a basis of E . Then, $e_i \cdot e_j = \sum_{k \in \Lambda} a_{ij}^k e_k$, for any $a_{ij}^k \in K$, where only a finite number of *structure constants* a_{ij}^k are not null, for some $i, j \in \Lambda$ fixed. Under these conditions, Tian defined an *evolution algebra* as the one for which exists a basis that verifies $a_{ij}^k = 0$, if $i \neq j$ (that is, $e_i \cdot e_j = 0$, if $i \neq j$). This basis is called *natural*. After renaming the structure constants, one can write $e_i \cdot e_i = \sum_{j=1}^v a_{ji} e_j$.

Particular cases of evolution algebras are the following.

If the defining relations are given by $e_i \cdot e_j = 0$, for all i and j , the algebra generated by these generators is said to be a *zero evolution algebra*.

If the defining relations are $e_i \cdot e_j = 0$, for $i \neq j$ and $e_i^2 = \alpha e_i$, for some $\alpha \in K$, the algebra is said to be a *nonzero trivial evolution algebra*.

If the defining relations are $e_i^2 = \sum_{e_k \in V_i} e_k$, $e_i \cdot e_j = 0$, $i \neq j$; $i, j = 1, 2, \dots, r$, where V_i is a subset of the set V , the evolution algebra is called *graphicable evolution algebra*.

It is obvious that every graphicable algebra is an evolution algebra, although the converse is not true, in general.

1.2 Hierarchy of an evolution algebra

The main definitions and results shown by Tian in his book [2] about the concept of *hierarchy* of an evolution algebra were the following

Definition 1.1 *An evolution algebra is said to be*

- connected, *if it does not admit a decomposition in direct sum of two proper subalgebras.*
- simple, *if it has no proper evolution ideals.*
- irreducible, *if it has no proper subalgebras.*

Recall that for Tian, a *subalgebra* of an evolution algebra E with natural basis V , is every closed subset on E that is generated by a subset of V .

Theorem 1.2 (Decomposition Theorem) *Let E be a connected evolution algebra. If it is considered as a vector space, then E admits the following decomposition in direct sum of subspaces*

$$E = A_1 \oplus A_2 \oplus \cdots \oplus \dot{+} B, \quad (1)$$

where all the A_i , $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$, are simple evolution subalgebras, $A_i \cap A_j = \{0\}$, for $i \neq j$ and B is a subspace generated by algebraically transient generators (what Tian denominates a transient space).

In that expression, the summation $A_1 \oplus A_2 \oplus \cdots \oplus A_n$ is a direct sum of subalgebras and the symbol $\dot{+}$ denotes a direct sum of subspaces. Tian calls this decomposition a *semidirect-sum decomposition* of an evolution algebra.

Note that, defining an induced multiplication in B_0 , denoted by \cdot^1 , in the following way

$$e_{0,i} \cdot^1 e_{0,j} = \rho_{B_0}(e_{0,i} \cdot e_{0,j}), \quad (2)$$

being ρ_{B_0} the projection of E onto B_0 , then B_0 , equipped with this new product, becomes an evolution algebra and so we can apply the Theorem 1.2 to it, obtaining

$$B_0 = A_{1,1} \oplus A_{1,2} \oplus \cdots \oplus A_{1,n_1} \dot{+} B_1,$$

where all the $A_{1,i}$, $i = 1, \dots, n_1$ are simple evolution subalgebras of B_0 , $A_{1,i} \cap A_{1,j} = \{0\}$, if $i \neq j$, and B_1 is the first transient space spanned by the first algebraically transient generators. This process can be repeated until we reach the i -th level where the transient space becomes trivial (that is, $B_i = \{0\}$).

Definition 1.3 (Hierarchy of an evolution algebra) *The hierarchy of an evolution algebra is defined as the decomposition obtained by applying successively the Theorem 1.2 to the algebra E and to the algebras B_i (with the induced product defined above) generated by algebraically transient generators (see Section 1.4).*

1.3 Theoretical aspects of the hierarchy of a generic algebra

This section is a reminder of the theoretical study carried out in citeAbraham to generalize the previous ideas on hierarchy on evolution algebras given by Tian in [2] to the case of any algebra in general.

From here on, \mathfrak{g} will denote a finite n -dimensional algebra defined over a n -dimensional K -vector space V and $\mathfrak{B} = \{e_1, \dots, e_n\}$ will be a basis of \mathfrak{g} .

Definition 1.4 (Persistent set) *Let $S = \{e_i\}_{i \in \Lambda} \subset \mathfrak{B}$ a subset of generators of \mathfrak{g} . S is said to be a persistent set if for all $i, j \in \Lambda$ there exist $e_{ij_1}, \dots, e_{ij_p} \in S$, and $a_1, \dots, a_p \in K$ such that*

$$e_i \cdot e_j = \sum_{k=1}^p a_k e_{ij_k} \quad (3)$$

Otherwise, the set S is said to be transient.

Tian's characterization of algebraic persistency of the generators of an evolution algebra involved the definition of the *occurrence* of a generator in another one. Tian says that a generator *occurs* in other if the first appears in the expression of the square of the second one as a linear combination of the basis elements. In citeAbraham Tian's *occurrence* concept was generalized through the introduction of a new concept: the *appearance* of a generator in the product of two others. It allows us to characterize the persistency of a set through its relationship with another certain set.

Definition 1.5 (Appearance of a generator in the product of two others) *It is said that the generator $e_k \in \mathfrak{B}$ appears in $e_i \cdot e_j$, which is denoted by $e_k \dashv e_i \cdot e_j$, if $a_k \neq 0$ in the expression 3.*

The following results, which were proved in citeAbraham, allow to obtain the Decomposition Theorem cited at the end of these paragraphs.

Proposition 1.6 *Let the subset $S = \{e_i\}_{i \in \Lambda} \subset \mathfrak{B}$ formed by generators and consider the set defined by*

$$M = \{e \in \mathfrak{B} \mid \exists i, j \in \Lambda, \text{ with } e \dashv e_i \cdot e_j\} \quad (4)$$

Then, S is persistent if and only if $M \subseteq S$.

Definition 1.7 *A persistent subset of a set of generators of an algebra is said to be simple if there is no persistent set strictly contained in it.*

Proposition 1.8 *If $S = \{e_i\}_{i \in \Lambda} \subset \mathfrak{B}$ is a simple persistent set, then $\langle S \rangle$ is a simple subalgebra of \mathfrak{g} , where $\langle S \rangle$ denotes the algebra spanned by S .*

Lemma 1.9 *Let $S_1 = \{e_1 \dots e_k\} \subset \mathfrak{B}$ and $S_2 = \{e_{k+1} \dots e_m\}$ ($m \leq n$) be two persistent sets of the algebra \mathfrak{g} , and let $A_1 = \langle S_1 \rangle$, $A_2 = \langle S_2 \rangle$ be two subalgebras, respectively spanned by S_1 and S_2 . Then, it is verified that*

1. S_i is a system of generators of A_i , $i = 1, 2$.
2. $A_1 \oplus A_2 = \langle e_1 \dots e_m \rangle$ (as vector spaces).

Theorem 1.10 (Decomposition Theorem) *Let \mathfrak{g} be a generic n -dimensional algebra, defined over a K -vector space V of dimension n , and $\mathfrak{B} = \{e_1, \dots, e_n\}$ a basis of \mathfrak{g} . Then \mathfrak{g} , considered as a vector space, admits a decomposition in a direct sum of subspaces as follows*

$$\mathfrak{g} = A_1 \oplus A_2 \oplus \dots \oplus A_m \dot{+} B,$$

where A_i , $i = 1, 2 \dots m$ are all simple subalgebras of \mathfrak{g} , with $A_i \cap A_j = \{0\}$ for $i \neq j$, B is the vector subspace generated by a transient set of generators, and where \oplus stands for the direct sum of subalgebras and $\dot{+}$ for the direct sum of vector subspaces. This decomposition is named as semidirect sum decomposition of an algebra.

1.4 Construction of the hierarchy of a generic algebra

According to previous study, in citeAbraham is construct the hierarchy of any algebra \mathfrak{g} and it is also shown an algorithmic procedure to obtain it. This algorithmic procedure had the following steps, from which the concept of hierarchy for a generic algebra is introduced.

Step 1: Level 0 of the hierarchy of the algebra.

As proved in the Theorem 1.10, \mathfrak{g} can be decomposed as

$$\mathfrak{g} = A_1 \oplus A_2 \oplus \dots \oplus A_m \dot{+} B_0,$$

where, according to the proof of the mentioned theorem, B_0 is a vector space generated by a set of transient generators.

The next level is defined as follows

Step 2: Level 1 of the hierarchy of the algebra.

If Λ is the set of indexes of the set of generators $\{e_i\}_{i \in \Lambda} \subset \mathfrak{g}$, we name by $e_{0,k}$ the generators of B_0 , with $k \in \Lambda_0 \subset \Lambda$. We define the induced product in B_0 , denoted by $\overset{1}{\cdot}$, as follows

$$e_{0,i} \overset{1}{\cdot} e_{0,j} = \rho_{B_0}(e_{0,i} \cdot e_{0,j}),$$

where ρ_{B_0} is the projection of \mathfrak{g} onto B_0 . Note that B_0 , endowed with that product, inherits the algebra structure from \mathfrak{g} . Then, we call B_0 the first algebra induced by \mathfrak{g} . Applying the Theorem 1.10 to the algebra $(B_0, \overset{1}{\cdot})$, we obtain that

$$B_0 = A_{1,1} \oplus A_{1,2} \oplus \dots \oplus A_{1,n_1} \dot{+} B_1,$$

where all $A_{1,i}$, $i = 1, 2 \dots n_1$ are simple subalgebras of B_0 , verifying that $A_{1,i} \cap A_{1,j} = \{0\}$, if $i \neq j$, and B_1 is the vector subspace generated by a set of transient generators in B_0 , named as *first transient subspace*. Applying the same idea to B_1 , the second level is obtained.

Step 3: Next levels of the hierarchy of the algebra.

After applying the first two steps as many times as necessary, the following decomposition is obtained

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{g} &= A_{0,1} \oplus A_{0,2} \oplus \dots \oplus A_{0,n_0} \dot{+} B_0 \\ B_0 &= A_{1,1} \oplus A_{1,2} \oplus \dots \oplus A_{1,n_1} \dot{+} B_1 \\ B_1 &= A_{2,1} \oplus A_{2,2} \oplus \dots \oplus A_{2,n_2} \dot{+} B_2 \\ &\dots\dots\dots \\ B_{m-1} &= A_{m,1} \oplus A_{m,2} \oplus \dots \oplus A_{m,n_m} \dot{+} B_m \\ B_m &= B_{m,1} \oplus B_{m,2} \oplus \dots \oplus B_{m,h}, \end{aligned}$$

where $A_{k,l}$ is the k -th simple subalgebra of level l , $A_{k,l} \cap A_{k,p} = \{0\}$, if $l \neq p$ and B_k is the k -th transient vector subspace, generated by a set of transient generators in B_{k-1} .

In the last level there is no residual vector space, and that is the reason for the algorithm to end at this precise point (note that this level is reached in any case, as we are working with finite-dimensional vector spaces).

The simple algebras of B_k are called *heads* of the hierarchy, being h the number of heads.

Definition 1.11 (Hierarchy of an algebra) *The term hierarchy of an algebra stands for the decomposition of an algebra in semi-sums of its subalgebras as constructed in the previous algorithmic procedure.*

Note that, according to this Decomposition Theorem 1.10, the hierarchy of an algebra is built over the fundamental concept of simple subalgebra, or equivalently, by linearity, the simple persistent set of generators. This allows us to prove the following two results

Proposition 1.12 *Two isomorphic algebras have the same hierarchy.*

Proposition 1.13 *The hierarchy of any n -dimensional Lie algebra \mathfrak{g} , with basis $\{e_1, \dots, e_n\}$, is*

$$A_{0,i} = \{e_i\}, \quad 1 \leq i \leq n \tag{5}$$

1.5 The algorithm

In [1], authors observed that computationally, the construction of algorithms that deal with the hierarchy of generic algebras was related with two main concepts that must be kept in mind due to their fundamental character

- The minimal persistent set which contains e_i , denoted by $MP(e_i)$
- The set of generators that must be taken into account to build $MP(e_i)$, denoted by $search(i)$

Both concepts lead to the following algorithm

Input: Product rule of an algebra \mathfrak{g} , $e_i \cdot e_j = \sum_{k=1}^n \alpha_{ijk} e_k$

Output: Hierarchy of \mathfrak{g}

begin

set $m = 0$

set $n = 1$

while $dim(\mathfrak{g}) > 0$ **do**

set $N := dim(\mathfrak{g})$

for $i \in \{1, \dots, N\}$ **do**

set $MP(e_i) = \{e_i\}$

set $search(i) = \emptyset$

for $j \in (\{1, \dots, N\} \setminus \{i\})$ **do**

if $\alpha_{ijj} \neq 0$ **then**

$e_j \in MP(e_i)$

$(i, j), (j, i), (j, j) \in search(i)$

end if

end for

for $(\tilde{i}, \tilde{j}) \in search(i)$ **do**

for $k \in \{1, \dots, N\}$ **do**

if $\alpha_{\tilde{i}\tilde{j}k} \neq 0 \wedge e_k \notin MP(e_i)$ **then**

$e_k \in MP(e_i)$

$(l, k) \in search(i) \forall l \in MP(e_i), l \neq k$

$(k, l) \in search(i) \forall l \in MP(e_i), l \neq k$

$(k, k) \in search(i)$

end if

end for

end for

end for

for $i \in \{1, \dots, N\}$ **do**

if $e_j \in MP(e_k) \forall e_j, e_k \in MP(e_i)$ **then**

set $A_{m,n} = MP(e_i)$

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    set  $n = n + 1$ 
    set  $\mathfrak{g} = \mathfrak{g} \setminus MP(e_i)$ 
  end if
end for
set  $m = m + 1$ 
end while
end

```

1.6 Preimage Algorithm

By considering the rules attached to the verification procedure to form the subalgebras, we can develop a method that provides random algebras matching a certain hierarchy.

We must note the following:

- As a consequence of the $MP(e_i)$ construction proceeding it is clear that $e_j \in MP(e_i) \Rightarrow MP(e_j) \subseteq MP(e_i)$. Then, the $A_{m,n}$ construction criteria requires that, given $\mathcal{B}_{A_{m,n}} = \{e_{m,n_i}\}_{1 \leq i \leq \dim(A_{m,n})}$, it is satisfied that $MP(e_{m,n_i}) = MP(e_{m,n_j}) \forall 1 \leq i, j \leq \dim(A_{m,n})$. As a consequence of this, we immediately observe that coupling $\mathcal{B}_{A_{m,n}}$ pairwise can be achieved by reciprocally relating the elements, i.e. by making $e_{m,n_j} \dashv e_{m,n_i} \cdot e_{m,n_i} \forall 1 \leq i, j \leq \dim(A_{m,n}) \parallel i \neq j$.
- In order to settle $A_{m,n}$ within the m th ($m > 1$) depth level, all its generators must satisfy $e_{m-1,o_j} \dashv e_{m,n_i} \cdot e_{m,n_i} \forall 1 \leq i \leq \dim(A_{m,n}); 1 \leq j \leq \dim(A_{m-1,o}); 1 \leq o \leq N_{m-1}$, i.e. they must be all directly related with all the generators appearing in the previous depth level.
- We can freely relate in a crossed way the generators from one depth level with all the previous depth levels: we either take $e_{m,n_i} \cdot e_{o,p_j}, e_{o,p_j} \cdot e_{m,n_i} \neq 0$ or not, where m precedes o . The direct relations from the previous bulletpoint makes that when deleting the previous depth levels from the basis this freedom becomes eradicated, avoiding more coupling than that matching the hierarchy.
- The relations between elements appearing across the same depth level must be considered meticulously in order not to jeopardize the desired structure. For $e_{m,n_i} \in \mathcal{B}_{A_{m,n}}; e_{m,o_j} \in \mathcal{B}_{A_{m,o}}$, where $n \neq o$, we may allow in general $e_{m,n_i} \cdot e_{m,o_j} \neq 0$ as these are not tightly coupled. A tighter coupling, meaning $n = o$, forces us to only consider $e_{l,p_k} \dashv e_{m,n_i} \cdot e_{m,n_j}$, where either $l < m$ or $l = m \wedge p = n$, that is we just allow appearance of elements from either previous depth levels or the same depth and same subalgebra.

It has been tested that quite random and general forms for the input are obtained y employing this algorithm. Hence, authors hypothetize this algorithm nearly characterizes an inverse of the hierarchy function.

E.g., it is easy to check that the examples provided in [1] emerge as a specific case of this method.

The algorithm results in the following:

Input: a hierarchy $\{\{\mathbf{A}_{m,n}\}_{1 \leq n \leq N_m}\}_{0 \leq m \leq M}$ and $\mathcal{P} = \{[0, p(0)]\} \cup \{[\beta_w, p(\beta_w)]\}_w$, where $\beta_w \in \mathbb{K} \setminus \{0\}$ and $p(x)$ are the probabilities of appearance, obviously satisfying $p(0) + \sum_w p(\beta_w) = 1$. We will later use $\mathcal{P} \setminus \{[0, p(0)]\}$ and will have to employ renormalized probabilities.

Output: the product rules α_{ijk} of an algebra \mathfrak{g} matching with the previous hierarchy.

begin

set $\alpha_{ijk} = 0 \ \forall i, j, k$

for $0 \leq m \leq M$ **do**

set $\mathcal{B}_m = \bigsqcup_{n \in N_m} \mathcal{B}_{A_{n,m}}$

for $e_{m_i} \in \mathcal{B}_m$ **do**

set $\alpha_{m_i m_i m_i} = \text{random choice } \mathcal{P}$

end for

for $1 \leq n, \hat{n} \leq N_m$ **do**

for $(e_{mn_i}, e_{m\hat{n}_j}) \in \mathcal{B}_{A_{m,n}} \times \mathcal{B}_{A_{m,\hat{n}}} \ \parallel \ e_{mn_i} \neq e_{m\hat{n}_j}$ **do**

if $n = \hat{n}$ **then**

set $\alpha_{(mn_i)(mn_i)(mn_j)} = \text{random choice } \mathcal{P} \setminus \{[0, p(0)]\}$

set $\alpha_{(mn_j)(mn_j)(mn_i)} = \text{random choice } \mathcal{P} \setminus \{[0, p(0)]\}$

for $e_w \in (\bigsqcup_{l < m} \mathcal{B}_l) \sqcup \mathcal{B}_{A_{m,n}}$ **do**

set $\alpha_{(mn_i)(mn_j)w} = \text{random choice } \mathcal{P}$

set $\alpha_{(mn_j)(mn_i)w} = \text{random choice } \mathcal{P}$

end for

else

for $e_w \in \mathcal{B}_{\mathfrak{g}}$ **do**

set $\alpha_{(mn_i)(mn_j)w} = \text{random choice } \mathcal{P}$

set $\alpha_{(mn_j)(mn_i)w} = \text{random choice } \mathcal{P}$

end for

end if

end for

end for

if $m \geq 1$ **then**

for $e_{m_i} \in \mathcal{B}_m$ **do**

for $e_j \in \bigsqcup_{p < m} \mathcal{B}_p$ **do**

for $e_k \in \mathcal{B}_{\mathfrak{g}}$ **do**

set $\alpha_{m_i l_j k} = \text{random choice } \mathcal{P}$

set $\alpha_{l_j m_i k} = \text{random choice } \mathcal{P}$

if $e_j \in \mathcal{B}_{m-1}$ **then**

set $\alpha_{m_i m_i k} = \text{random choice } \mathcal{P} \setminus \{[0, p(0)]\}$

end for

end for

end for

```

else
  set  $\alpha_{m_i m_i k} = \text{random choice } \mathcal{P}$ 
end if
end for
end for
end for
end if
end for

```

2 The computational study of the hierarchy algorithm

We now proceed to study both the time and space complexity of the latter pseudocode.

The main sources of time complexity come from the outer *while* loop, the construction process of each $MP(e_i)$ and the verification of the conditions over the $MP(e_i)$ to build the $A_{m,n}$.

2.1 Worst Case Time Complexity

In [1] authors focus on the following algebras in order to grasp the time complexity:

$$\begin{cases} e_i \cdot e_i &= e_{i+1} & (1 \leq i \leq n-1) \\ e_i \cdot e_{i+1} &= e_1 & (1 \leq i \leq n-1) \\ e_i \cdot e_j &= 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

These algebras are defined in such a way that they present a recursive behavior when the Decomposition Theorem 1.10 is applied to them.

These conform a convenient example of computationally demanding algebras as these reach the maximum plausible depth for the hierarchy and they verify that for each iteration $iter \exists! j_{0,iter} \parallel$

$$\begin{aligned} MP(e_i)_{iter} &= \mathcal{B}_{iter}, \quad search(i)_{iter} = \mathcal{B}_{iter} \times \mathcal{B}_{iter} \setminus \{(i, i)\} \quad \forall i \neq j_{0,iter} \\ MP(e_{j_{0,iter}}) &= \{e_{j_{0,iter}}\}, \quad search(j_{0,iter}) = \emptyset \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where \mathcal{B}_{iter} is the basis after $iter$ iterations of the algorithm; i.e. with exception of a single basis element $MP(e_i)$, $search(i)$ reach its maximum possible size. Authors of that article hypothesize these are near to the worst case complexity. We can obtain from the preimage algorithm more demanding cases by taking more dense preimages, though the resulting runtimes do not exceed those of the \mathfrak{g}_n by too much (as they do not present much room for getting more complex).

By rough calculation we can estimate the time complexity of the algorithm. We have to consider both the construction procedure of the $MP(e_i)$, $search(i)$ and the verification

of the necessary condition of the $MP(e_i)$. The latter one, altogether with the outer *while* loop, takes $\mathcal{O}(n^5)$ to execute. Secondly we have to estimate the time needed to construct the auxiliary sets. It is complicated to exactly compute the time complexity of this section. Nevertheless, we must bear in mind that for each duple in $search(i)$ we have only one $\hat{k} \in \{1, \dots, N\}$ leading to $\alpha_{ij\hat{k}} \neq 0$ and therefore enabling further operations. Then, it is easy to check that this part of the process also takes $\mathcal{O}(n^5)$ at most to execute.

The algorithm was transcribed to a local version of Python 3.10 and later executed in a computer with the following components: Intel i7 4770 (3.4 GHz CPU), 16.00 GBs of DDR3 RAM (1600 MHz).

We proceed to measure the runtimes of these precise examples until reaching high dimensions. Several measures for each dimension were performed in order to reduce the error.

A curve fit on the obtained data is done for consecutive polynomial models around the expected order of complexity and write down the order of the polynomial that maximizes the goodness of the fit. In order to avoid overfitting, data was split onto a fitting and a validation set. Both the maximum R^2 and minimum validation $RMSE$ were obtained for a 5th degree regression model (Figure 1). Such result was tested for a range of proportions between the fitting and the validation set, raising the same observations.

Figure 1: average runtimes plotted against dimension for the proposed \mathfrak{g}_n . The curve that best fits the data and minimizes the mean squared errors for the validation data is a 5th degree polynomial.

Implementing a power model also provides a worst case complexity of $\mathcal{O}(n^5)$. This comes as enough evidence to state that, as predicted, the algorithm develops across the dimensions as a quintic function.

2.2 A Hint on the Statistics of Hierarchies: Average Runtime Growth of a General Algebra

Amongst a myriad of algebras we have just analysed a really challenging case in terms of computation. This may not give an idea of the actual efficiency of the algorithm when executed for a random given product rule.

To get the mean time complexity of the algorithm it was tested for 100 random 3-order tensors for each dimension. By analogy with the previous section a curve fit of the averaged runtimes was performed, yielding a time complexity of $\mathcal{O}(n^4)$ (Figure 2). That is, the algorithm is in general more efficient w.r.t. the theoretical prediction obtained via rough calculation. It is due to the fact that for increasing dimension more intricate hierarchies become rare, making that product rules corresponding to the most basic hierarchies spoil the statistics. These hierarchies run a low number of iterations of the outer *while* loop, hence provoking a time complexity of $\mathcal{O}(n^4)$ instead.

Figure 2: average runtimes plotted against dimension for a sample of random product rules. The curve that best fits the data and minimizes the mean squared errors for the validation set is a 4th degree polynomial.

2.3 Effect of input and output structure on runtimes.

Product rules may vary largely in complexity without even affecting the output hierarchy they induce. Developing intuitive and meaningful metrics on the structure of these 3-order tensors becomes hard. Because of this we will focus on the most obvious source of complexity: the sparsity of the product rules. As a metric of the sparsity of a product rule we can intuitively use:

Definition 2.1 (Sparsity of the Product Rules) *We take the sparsity of the product rules of a general algebra \mathfrak{g} as the ratio of the non-zero coefficient of the product rules wrt*

total as

$$\mathcal{S}(\mathfrak{g}) = \frac{\text{card}(\alpha_{ijk} \neq 0)}{\text{dim}(\mathfrak{g})^3} \quad (8)$$

, where α_{ijk} encodes the product rules.

The hierarchy of an algebra is, on the other hand, much simpler and enables us to use more creative ways to characterize the structure of the output. We will mainly use some sort of coupling factor as a metric of the output intricacy. It should become larger for hierarchies featuring larger subalgebras at deeper levels. A first intuitive choice would be to couple each subalgebra with all the basis elements appearing throughout the previous depth levels. Nevertheless, this function is not well behaved, returning extremely high values sometimes. Our second choice would be polynomial instead of recursive. Eventually we used the following metric:

Definition 2.2 (Coupling Factor of a Hierarchy) *As a measure of the complexity of a hierarchy, related with the size of the auxiliary sets of the hierarchy algorithm, we use the sum*

$$\mathcal{CF}(\{A_{m,n}\}_{m,n}) = \sum_{m,n} (m+1)^2 \cdot \text{dim}(A_{m,n})^2 \quad (9)$$

As amongst the vast landscape of product rules those with increasingly more complex hierarchies become more rare as stated in section 2.2, we will use the preimage algorithm from section 1.6 to get a more varied sample that evaluates the bond between runtimes and the coupling factor.

Random hierarchies were created ranging from 1 to 30 in dimension, sweeping all possible depths and we considered $\mathcal{P} = \{[0, p], [1, 1 - p]\}$, where p takes 50 equispaced values from 0 to 1. Its coupling factor was measured. Then the preimage algorithm was executed on them to get random corresponding product rules. Its sparsity was measured. Then the hierarchy computation was performed from these product rules to measure the runtimes.

Firstly, from Figure 3, we infer that the runtimes present a positive significant correlation ($R = 0.92$) with the coupling factor. However, a slight cone shape is obtained, thus indicating underlying heteroscedasticity is going on and thus the coupling factor model employed can be improved.

In Figure 4 it is observed that for low sparsities execution time becomes diminished. However, past from this low sparsity region runtimes do slightly increase as more relations are added. This effect becomes more acute for larger dimensions when compared with smaller ones. It is because a same increase on sparsity leads to a larger addition of bonds in the case of higher dimension. The decrease shown in the curve fit when approaching full sparsity is a mere consequence of overfitting of outliers and must be ignored. It was

not observed when carrying out the same study over specific hierarchies and its preimages.

Figure 3: runtimes plotted against the proposed metric for coupling factor. A high correlation between these magnitudes is gotten. Slight heteroscedasticity is observed, indicating the \mathcal{CF} model can be improved.

Figure 4: runtimes plotted against \mathcal{CF} and sparsity. A slight increment on runtimes is observed as sparsity gets larger.

From the previous discussions we can derive that sparsity has a slight impact on execution time and it becomes increasingly relevant with dimension. Moreover, the coupling factor explains well the creation of new complex bonds between basis elements and its effect on the runtimes.

2.4 Complexity for Evolution Algebras

In the specific case of evolution algebras we can ensure the existence of a basis for which the product rules become diagonal.

By analogy with the general case, we will derive the time complexity in this case by averaging the runtimes of a large sample of product rules. To generate these product rules we will begin with the root (but random and not unique) case of a diagonal product rule and then we will transform it via applying nonsingular transformations to the basis.

Let $e_i \cdot e_i = \sum_{j=1}^n \alpha_{ij} e_j$ be a root case. Let $A = (a_{ij})_{ij}$ be a $n \times n$ regular matrix. Let $\{v_i = Ae_i\}_{i=1}^n$ be the new basis. Then, its product rules will be $v_x \cdot v_y = (\sum_{i=1}^n a_{ix} e_i) \cdot (\sum_{j=1}^n a_{jy} e_j) = \sum_{i=1}^n a_{ix} \alpha_{iy} e_i^2 = \sum_{j=1}^n \beta_{xyj} e_j$, where $\beta_{xyj} = \sum_{i=1}^n a_{ix} \alpha_{ij} a_{iy}$. We look for $\sum_{j=1}^n \beta_{xyj} e_j = \sum_{k=1}^n \gamma_{xyk} v_k = \sum_{k=1}^n \gamma_{xyk} \cdot \sum_{j=1}^n a_{jk} e_j = \sum_{j=1}^n (\sum_{k=1}^n a_{jk} \gamma_{xyk}) e_j$ and thus $\sum_{k=1}^n a_{jk} \gamma_{xyk} = \sum_{k=1}^n a_{kx} \alpha_{kkj} a_{ky} \forall j$. Hence,

$$\underline{\gamma}_{xy} = A^{-1} \cdot \alpha^t \cdot \underline{v}_x \odot \underline{v}_y \quad (10)$$

, where \odot denotes the pointwise vector product and $\alpha = (\alpha_{kkj})_{kj}$.

This connects two quite different types of vector products. In addition, it remains coherent with the commutative nature of evolution algebras.

A large sample of random evolution algebras' product rules was built implementing these transformations of root cases. No major differences were measured for the runtimes with respect to the general case. Therefore, restriction to the case of evolution algebras does not simplify the computation process of the hierarchy.

A historical perspective of these algebras can be checked in [5] and more related information can be consulted in other sources ([6] and [7] for instance).

2.5 Space complexity

The space complexity of the algorithm is determined by the input and the two auxiliary sets, $MP(e_i)$ and $search(i)$. The latter ones mostly contribute to the space complexity within the first iteration of the while loop as these become diminished in length throughout the following iterations. At worst, each $MP(e_i)$, $search(i)$ will contribute $\mathcal{O}(n)$, $\mathcal{O}(n^2)$ respectively, yielding a total of $\mathcal{O}(n^3)$. This will always lead, considering the $\mathcal{O}(n^3)$ contribution from the input, to a cubic space complexity.

This was first tested in the previously commented computer, whose limited components didn't enable us to reach fairly high dimensions within a reasonable simulation time. Slow growth was observed across the first 100 dimensions, making it necessary to export the

code to a more capable computer in order to obtain more meaningful data for the curve fit. It was eventually tested in a local version of Python 3.12.7 with a computer consisting of the following components: Intel i7-10700 (2.9-4.8 GHz), 32 GBs of DDR4 RAM (2667 MHz).

Memory usage was pinpointed several times within each dimension until reaching dimension 200, 150 for the average case and the worst one respectively. The several measurements were manually executed so that there was a time gap between each execution, enabling us to minimize fluctuations of the base memory when taking the average of the data. The resulting data was scatter-plotted and tested for consecutive polynomial models of regression both for the worst and random cases (Figure 5). A validation set was also generated taking intermediate as well as further dimensions.

Figure 5: At the left the avg memory usage for the worst cases scatter-plotted against dimension. At the right for random product rules. A 3rd degree polynomial best fits the data.

It was found that a 3rd degree polynomial optimizes the fit and validation goodness for both cases. Moreover, performing a power fit provided confidence intervals exceeding 2 and approaching 3 for the exponents in both situations.

3 Some Examples of Algebras and its Hierarchies

As a convention product rules will be represented by its 3-order tensors using voxels. Depending on sparsity, it will be more convenient to either plot the non-zero entries or the opposite. It will be indicated by the color of the voxels: blue for boolean voxels and red for inverted boolean voxels.

On the other hand, hierarchies will be plotted as matrix colormaps where the rows and

columns represent the depth level and basis element respectively. Within each depth level the same color is assigned to matrix elements conforming a single subalgebra. This provides a faster and more clear understanding of the input and output structure.

The worst case example from [1] can be visualized for 10th dimension as in Figure 6. From the preimage algorithm developed in section 1.6 we can also get the previous hierarchy from a much more dense product rules structure (Figure 6). Both examples present pretty different sparsities (0.018 and 0.955 respectively). Nevertheless, the runtime from the first is slightly lower than the one from the second example (5.76 and 7.63 ms respectively).

Figure 6: At the left the product rules of the \mathfrak{g}_{10} represented with boolean voxels, where just non-null entries are plotted. At the right its hierarchy, $\bigoplus_{i=10}^1 \langle e_i \rangle$, as a matrix colormap. Between these two, the product rules of the most dense preimage of the hierarchy $\bigoplus_{i=10}^1 \langle e_i \rangle$ represented with inverted boolean voxels, i.e. just null entries were plotted.

The next example (Figure 7) can help us gain more intuition about the process described in section 1.6. The \mathcal{CF} of this hierarchy is 182, much lower compared to the one for \mathfrak{g}_{10} : 385. We therefore obtain lower runtimes: 1.7, 5.5 *ms* for the least and most dense case respectively. Sparsity variation is narrower this time (0.026 and 0.933), yet runtime difference is much larger. It is due to the fact that the \mathfrak{g}_n presented little room for getting more complex as their auxiliary sets were already the most possibly complex ones. However, in general we have much more margin to fill the auxiliary sets as we increase sparsity.

4 Conclusions and open problems

At present, note that in current mathematics, the computational treatment of any theoretical study carried out on any topic is very important, since it allows, on the one hand, to confirm the results obtained in the theoretical study and, on the other, to open new possibilities of research on questions that may arise regarding that study. Indeed, a computational treatment accompanies practically all the current theoretical studies carried out, therefore it can be considered to be another part of pure mathematics when not long ago this treatment was considered to correspond to applied mathematics.

Figure 7: At the right a proposed hierarchy as a matrix colormap. At the left the boolean voxels representing the most sparse product rule matching that hierarchy. Between these two the inverted boolean voxels representing the most dense product rules that provoke that precise hierarchy.

Some years ago, one of the authors of this article, together with other collaborators, carried out research on the concept of hierarchy of algebras in general and evolution algebras in particular (see [1]). This is a concept which until that moment had been little studied, and that still continues to be barely treated by researchers. However, the computational treatment of the study carried out was quite scarce and was limited to revealing some small aspects related to complexity and computational time. In this article the authors address in much more depth and extension the computational treatment carried out by Cruz et al.

The most relevant results obtained by the authors have been the following

- Time complexity is $\mathcal{O}(n^5)$. This confirms the statement made in [1] that the algorithm's complexity is polynomial yet requires many operations in between. Nevertheless, for the range of dimensions treated in this study for the time section (< 80) we have reasonable runtimes, making it feasible to work with the algorithm in this domain.
- Space complexity is $\mathcal{O}(n^3)$. This result is optimistic, as the demand on memory is fixed by the nature of the entry and the first iteration. Therefore, memory overflows can be detected early in the execution of the algorithm and should only occur for dimension intervals much greater than these shown in this work (< 200).
- Intricate hierarchies become more rare as dimension is increased, so evaluating the algorithm over random algebras usually leads to lower execution times, but does typically lead to basic outputs.
- Intricacy of the output is highly correlated with execution time. Complexity of the input has a much more slight effect with the exception of low sparsities, as first additions of non-essential relations become much more relevant. When applied to Evolution Algebras, the algorithm does not present a significantly different demand on the equipment.

And as Open Problems, the authors suggest the following

- Carrying out a computational study on different types of algebras. For example: Lie, Leibniz and Zinbiel algebras. They were not done in this work due to extension requirements.
- Developing more meaningful and better statistically behaved models and metrics both on the input and the output in order to get more neat regression and grasp more information on the relevant dependences in the hierarchy process.
- Studying the possibility of further optimization of the algorithm to reduce complexity and finding out more optimal representations of input data to lower space complexity.
- Finding further generalization of the preimage algorithm from section 1.6 if possible.
- Finding useful application of these procedures to discrete dynamical systems as proposed by Tian.

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